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#Stay-at-home #It-is-not-that-simple

Domina Petric, MD

It is not that simple to say: Stay at home! People in self-isolation, especially the elderly that might be isolated for a very long time, must be supplied with groceries and vital medications by caregivers (family members, volunteers or other caregivers insured by the government). Isolation strategies must be perfectly well paced to prevent transmission of the virus on the one hand, and on the other hand, isolation strategies must be stopped at the right time to prevent mental and physical health consequences.

As countries are affected by COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019), the elderly population are already or will soon be told to self-isolate for a very long time¹.

Social isolation among older adults is a serious public health concern because of their heightened risk of cardiovascular, autoimmune, neurocognitive, and mental health problems².

Santini and coworkers demonstrated in the study that social disconnection puts older adults at greater risk of depression and anxiety³.

Self-isolation will disproportionately affect elderly individuals whose only social contact is out of the home, such as at daycare venues, community centers, and places of worship. Those who do not have close family or friends, and rely on the support of voluntary services or social care

could be placed at additional risk, along with those who are already lonely, isolated, or secluded⁴.

The forced isolation perhaps cuts deepest for those in mourning. Joey Ayoub, a Lebanese researcher, said his grandfather died "this week" of problems unrelated to the coronavirus. He worries for his grandmother, who suddenly lives alone⁵.

It is not that simple to say: Stay at home! People in self-isolation, especially the elderly that might be isolated for a very long time, must be supplied with groceries and vital medications by caregivers (family members, volunteers or other caregivers insured by the government).

Second, urgent action is needed to mitigate the mental and physical health consequences⁴ of isolation strategies.

Third, isolation strategies must be perfectly well paced to prevent transmission of the virus on the one hand, and on the other hand, isolation strategies must be stopped at the right time to prevent mental and physical health consequences.

Fourth, it is important to understand that it is much easier for the rich people (who are provided with various contents in their homes) to live in self-isolation than it is for the poor people for which the sunlight and fresh air, or a short visit to the place of worship or community center, is everything in the world.

The effect of isolation will be felt greatest in more disadvantaged and marginalized populations, which should be urgently targeted for the implementation of preventive strategies⁴.

Interventions can be as simple as kind smile and short conversation when providing groceries to the self-isolated individual or more complex as on-line (for those with internet access) psychotherapy and after the lockdown is over, cognitive behavioral therapy.

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